

Arthropods Abundance and Diversity in Federal University Wukari's Farm, Taraba State, Nigeria

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Suggested Citation

Ronald, W.I.A., Numdi, F.C. & Twan, M.S. (2023). Arthropods Abundance and Diversity in Federal University Wukari's Farm, Taraba State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(6), 22-29.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(6\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(6).03)

Abstract:

Despite the fact that Federal University Wukari's farm has a huge area covered in grasses and trees, nothing is known about the variety, number, and species of the arthropods that live there. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the species richness, variety, and the abundance of arthropods present at the Federal University Wukari School farm. From September to November 2021, a total of 1698 unique arthropods were gathered, 32 species, 29 families, and 18 orders. Each month had an average of 618 to 550 arthropods, representing 27 to 30 different species. The fauna was dominated by Order Hymenoptera, which had 1110 individuals from 6 species.

With a rating of 5.106, September was the month with the most abundant and varied arthropods.

Keywords: *Species richness, abundance, arthropods, FUW, school farm, Taraba.*

Introduction

Arthropod is the most diverse and dominant constituent of biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems. It is the largest animal phylum constituting about 85% of all known animals in the world (Odegaard, 2000). Developments of infrastructures affect species' abundance, richness, composition, populations, and communities, because changes in community attributes influence the structures and functions of ecosystems. Undeveloped areas of Federal University Wukari, Taraba State (FUW) host a high abundance of arthropods, however, are continuously disturbed by human activities such as expansion of the university infrastructures and cutting of the grasses and cattle grazing. As

a result, many habitats of arthropods are declining, fragmented or isolated. Despite FUW having a large area covered by grasses and woods, little is known about the abundance, diversity, and species of arthropods inhabiting there. Despite the fact that the FUW has a significant area that is covered with grasses and forests, nothing is known about the amount, diversity, and species of arthropods that live there because a research to determine the variety and abundance of arthropods present has not been conducted. Arthropods' macro- and micro-habitats are been destroyed by on-going human activity. As a result, because arthropods are disturbance sensitive (Magurran, 2004), reduces the quantity, diversity, and richness of arthropods (Rainio, 2003). Therefore, this study

was conducted to evaluate the species richness, variety, and the abundance of arthropods found at the FUW School farm. It was specifically intended to ascertain whether the makeup of arthropod assemblages can vary at the school farm at Federal University

Study Area

Federal University Wukari, Taraba state is located in Wukari, a town in Taraba state North East Nigeria (fig. 1). It was founded in 2011. Its geographical coordinates are altitude 7°51'0"N and longitude 9°46'0"E. It has an area extent of 54,473km², making it the third largest state in Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Figure 1. Nigerian map with the Taraba State and Wukari local government area highlighted.

Source: Taraba State's Jalingo Ministry of Land and Survey

Ways for Collecting Arthropods

Arthropods were gathered in 2021 between September and November. Pitfall traps, sweep nets, beating sheets, and human hands were all used to physically gather them. Arthropods that had been collected were brought back to the lab and sorted to the species level using keys and guides (Martins, 2014). Arthropods that had been trapped were ethyl acetate-killed in the killing bottle before being recognized and preserved. For hard-bodied insects, the specimens were stretched, dried, pinned and stored in 70% ethyl alcohol for soft-bodied insects. The methods used to harvest arachnids are comparable to those.

Arthropod Collection Methods

Arthropods were collected from September to November, 2021. They were collected using pitfall traps, sweep nets, beating sheets and manually using hands. Collected arthropods were brought back to the laboratory and sorted with the help of keys and guides to species level (Martins, 2014). Trapped Arthropods were killed using ethyl acetate in the killing bottle before being identified and preserved. The specimens were stretched, dried, dry pinned (for hard bodied insects) and preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol (for soft bodied insects). Techniques used to collect Arthropod are similar to those of Balakrishnan *et al.* (2014); Adjaloo *et al.* (2012); Nazir *et al.* (2014); Belamkar, *et al.* (2012); Khadijah, *et al.* (2013); and Nyundo, *et al.* (2007) which is some of the publications that discuss this phenomenon.

Identification of Specimens

According to Winchester, 1992, arthropods were divided into their various Orders and families and recognized using common names in the species level. The specimen was identified in the biology laboratory of the department of Biological Sciences at Federal University Wukari in Taraba State. The species were classified alongside the appropriate families to which they belonged.

Statistical Analysis

The mean of the physical characteristics of the soil and arthropods at each site were compared statistically using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) method (Ogbeibu, 2005). Duncan's multiple comparison of means is used to assess how similar the sampling stations are to one another. Arthropods and soil physical characteristics were correlated, and this correlation was calculated. The difference between the physical characteristics of the soil between the rainy and dry seasons, as well as the seasonal fluctuation in the biotic community, was determined using the student t-test. The Shannon index, Equitability or Evenness, and species Richness indexes were used to measure the level of association among arthropod samples and within the species (Ogbeibu, 2005).

RESULTS

Fauna Composition

The occurrence of arthropod species in FUW for the month of September to November is shown in (Table 1). A total of 32 species belonging to 29 families of 18 orders namely; Hymenoptera, Diptera, Coleoptera, Orthoptera, Ixodida, Dermaptera, Lepidoptera, Spirobolida, Polydesmida, Isopoda, Hemiptera, Odonata, Mantodea, Araneae, Collembola, Dermaptera, Geophilomorpha and Blattodea. A total of 1698 individuals were collected from September to November. The total number of arthropods for each month ranges from 618 - 550 individuals and from 27 – 30species.

Hymenoptera (1110 individuals), Coleoptera (394 individuals), and Orthoptera (72 individuals) dominated the fauna, as illustrated in figure 2. The total number of species belonging to the various orders is depicted in Figure 3. The group of insects with the most species (six) was the hymenoptera.

Table 1. List of Arthropods Collected in FUW

Order	Family	Species	Sept	Oct	Nov	Total
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Dorylus nigricans molestus</i> (Soldier ant)	225	325	290	840
		<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i> (sugar ant)	20	50	40	110
		<i>Monomorium minimum</i> (little black ant)	50	30	70	150
	Apidae	<i>Apis cerana</i> (Asian honeybee)	1	0	0	1
		<i>Vespula germanica</i> (social wasp)	2	1	2	5
	Megachilidae	<i>Apis dorsata</i> (Giant honeybee)	1	0	0	1
Diptera	Muscidae	<i>Musca domestica</i> (House fly)	2	1	2	5
	Asilidae	<i>Brachycera sp</i> (robber fly)	1	1	0	2
	Bazaar fly	<i>Musca sorbens</i>	0	1	1	2
Coleoptera	Anobiidae	<i>Caenocara nigricone</i> (Anobiid beetle)	100	50	80	230
	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus melanarius</i> (rain beetle)	40	30	50	120
	Tenebrionidae	<i>Opatropis hispida</i> (darkling beetle)	10	5	20	35
	Langruriinae	<i>Microlanguria jansoni</i> (lizard beetle)	5	3	1	9
Orthoptera	Gryllidae	<i>Scapsipedus marginatus</i> (Cricket)	23	13	15	51
	Acrididae	<i>Melanoplus differentialis</i> (Grasshoppers)	9	7	5	21
Ixodida	Ixodidae	<i>Ixodes ricinus</i> (Ticks)	1	0	1	2
Dermaptera	Forficulidae	<i>Forficula auricularia</i> Earwigs	3	4	4	11
Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i> (adult butterfly)	3	4	10	17
	Noctuidae	<i>Pseudaletia unipuncta</i> (Army worm moth)	2	2	2	6
Spirobolida	Spirobolidae	<i>Narceus americanus</i> (millipede)	5	4	4	13
Polydesmida	Polydesmidae	<i>Harpaghe baydeniana</i> (yellow spotted millipede)	3	2	3	8
Isopoda	Armadillidiidae	<i>Armadillidum vulgare</i> (pill Bug)	1	0	0	1
Hemiptera	Corizidae	<i>Leptocoris trivittatus</i> (Boxelder bug)	0	0	1	1
Odonata	Calopterygidae	<i>Phaon iridipennis</i> (Dragon fly)	3	2	3	8
Mantodea	Mantidae	<i>Stagmomantis carolina</i> (praying matis)	3	4	2	9
Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Gasteracantha cancriformis</i> (orb-weaver Spider)	2	2	2	6
	Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge venusta</i> (orchard spider)	3	1	3	7
	Agelenidae	<i>Eratigena agrestis</i> (hobo spider)	1	1	2	4
Collembola	Sminthuridae	<i>Allacma fusca</i> (springtail)	1	0	0	1
Lithobiomorpha	Lithobiidae	<i>Lithobius forficatus</i> (garden centipedes)	2	1	2	5

Blattodea	Blattidae	<i>Periplaneta americana</i> (cockroach)	2	2	1	5
No of Individuals Per Month			527	550	618	1698
No Of Species			30	27	27	

Figure 2. Individual Numbers of Arthropods Collected from Federal University Wukari Taraba State School Farm from September to November

From September to November, the FUW School Farm's species richness (D) values were 5.106, 5.072, and 4.979, respectively.

From September to November, the diversity index (H^1) had values of 2.007, 1.640, and 1.908, respectively.

From September to November, the values of species equitability, evenness (E) were 0.320, 0.260, and 0.296, respectively.

The results of the soil analysis at FUW School Farm are as follows: % Organic Carbon 0.93% and % Organic Matter 1.60%. % Nitrogen 0.73%, Available Phosphorus 8.50%, pH in water 7.85%, Soil Texture (% Silt 26.40, Clay 8.00, Sand 65.60 and Textural Class Sandy Loam).

Figure 3. Number of Family Per Order of Arthropods Caught from FUU Taraba State School Farm

Discussion

In terrestrial ecosystems, arthropods make up the majority of biodiversity and are its most diversified component. In Taraba state, Nigeria, at the school farm of Federal University Wukari, the species richness and variety of arthropods were described in this study.

In the FUU school farm from the months of September through November, 1697 arthropods totalling 32 species from 30 families and 18 orders were collected using 10 traps, sweep nets, beating trays, and manual collection. The fauna was dominated by the orders Hymenoptera (65%), Coleoptera (23%) and Orthoptera (4%). This study showed that the FUU school farm's arthropod fauna is reasonably diversified and has moderate densities. The number of arthropods found in this study was slightly higher than that found in the Abaeku dumpsite in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria (Abbulimen, 2010), where there were 1081 individuals total, 1081 of which belonged to 26 species, 23 families, and 16 orders, but only one method of sampling, pitfall trap setting, which was done for a longer period

of time of a 6 month-research project compared with that of the FUU's 3 month-sample project. This demonstrates that despite having a rich habitat, arthropods cannot survive in a frequently disturbed area because Abaeku dumpsite was constantly being burned.

The capacity of Hymenoptera, Coleoptera, and Orthoptera to live in a variety of habitats allowed for their great abundance. The number of families was highest in the Order Coleoptera. Numerous research conducted worldwide (Balakrishnan *et al.*, 2014; Nazir *et al.*, 2014; Belamker and Jadesh, 2012; Khadijah *et al.*, 2013) have demonstrated the vast diversity of Coleopterans. With 325 individuals, the Hymenoptera species had the highest population in October. Due to their capacity to adapt to circumstances in the soil and litter layer, the complexity of vegetation, and the microclimate, hymenoptera displayed significant abundance in the FUU School farm (Lassau, 2005). Strong mouthparts and various life styles enable both larvae and adults to feed on a variety of meals and occupy a number of environmental niches (Lee *et al.*, 2013). The high Margalef index value

of 5.106 for the month of September indicates a high level of species richness. It demonstrated that compared to the other months, the overall number of captured arthropods was large.

Conclusion and Recommendations

There are only a few thriving species in this ecosystem, according to the moderate diversity and quantity of arthropod species in the FUW School Farm. Only a small number of arthropod species are suited on this ecosystem since there are presumably limited ecological niches and microhabitats. On the other hand, while food webs in the ecosystem appear to be very basic, they may have a significant impact on the diversity and abundance of arthropods. High species diversity and abundance in other habitats point to more successful arthropod species, a stable ecosystem, enough ecological niches, and microhabitats that is less prone to be disturbed. The findings suggest that the environment of grasslands has the capacity to support arthropod diversity and serve as a useful refuge for some arthropods from woodlands and other habitats.

This study also suggests that additional research be conducted to determine the variety and abundance of arthropods that live on the main site of the FUW School Farm.

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